

Best practice guidelines & resources Citizen Observatories

Description

This guideline is an output from the Cos4Cloud project which demonstrates best practice for Citizen Observatories (COs), based on the experiences of the COs involved in the project. Cos4Cloud includes the participation of [nine established citizen observatories](#) (COs) and Do it Yourself (DIY) initiatives including: [Artportalen](#), [CanAirIO](#), [FreshWater Watch](#), [iSPEX](#), [iSpotnature](#), [Kduino](#), [Natusfera](#), [OdourCollect](#). and [Pl@ntNet](#); which are all collectively referred to as COs.

These COs have contributed to the development of the [Cos4Cloud technological services](#) and this is one of the guidelines developed from these experiences. It is part of a collection in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub and shared as part of the legacy best practices and lessons learned from the project for other citizen observatories and initiatives.

Best Practice Guideline title

Guidelines on Best Practice for Citizen Observatories: a Cos4Cloud CO approach framed by the ECSA 10 Principles of citizen science

What is this best practice guideline about?

This guide demonstrates Cos4Cloud best practice developed from the implementation of the project. These examples are produced as guidelines for other COs, initiatives and interested stakeholders which if followed, can produce good outcomes. It highlights COs best practice in the context of the ECSA Ten Principles of citizen Science ([ECSA, 2015](#)) which has been applied as a framework for CO best practice. These principles are regarded as “a principled guide for all citizen science project developers and practitioners” ([Sturm, 2017](#)).

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

COs

Biodiversity COs

Environment COs

COs lead partners

BACKGROUND: THE COs INVOLVED IN COS4CLOUD

Co-designed Citizen Observatories Services for the European Open Science Cloud (Cos4Cloud, <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>), has developed thirteen technological services focused on boosting citizen science observatories to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations. Cos4Cloud includes **nine established citizen observatories (COs)** and Do it Yourself (DIY) initiatives

participating by integrating, testing and providing feedback; as well as acting as demonstrators sharing the services with their user communities. This includes:

Four focused on the biodiversity:

1. Artportalen
2. iSpotnature
3. Natusfera
4. Pl@ntNet

And five focused on the environment:

- CanAirIO
- FreshWater Watch
- iSPEX
- Kduino
- OdourCollect

Read summaries of the COs in Cos4Cloud [here](#).

Watch this video to find out more about their role in Cos4Cloud. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xvGqSdOJXuQ>

What are the achievements of the citizen observatories in Cos4Cloud?

What are citizen observatories?

In Cos4Cloud, COs are defined as research infrastructures i.e. technological platforms with a diverse range of tools that allow the development of citizen science projects, with an objective to include widescale participation, covering large geographical areas over long periods of time (Momino, 2017). Findings from research and analysis of COs highlights key attributes and characteristics, data collection tools and technologies; noting how these also present challenges to their sustainability. Cos4Cloud’s approach focused on providing support to COs by co-designing innovative technological services helping to meet some these challenges.

APPROACH: ECSA’S TEN PRINCIPLES OF CITIZEN SCIENCE AND COs

The European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) Ten Principles of Citizen Science (ECSA,2015) is recognised globally as one of the main guiding best practice framework for citizen science, and has themes of direct relevance to COs. “serving as a principled guide for all citizen science project developers and practitioners” (Sturm,et al, 2017).

Table 1: ECSA’s Ten Principles of Citizen Science framework: for the collation of best practice experiences of Cos4Cloud COs

ECSA - Ten Principles of Citizen Science (ECSA, 2015)
<p>1. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates new knowledge or understanding. Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.</p>
<p>2. Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome. For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.</p>
<p>3. Both the professional scientists and the citizen scientists benefit from taking part. Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence.</p>
<p>4. Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process. This may include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.</p>

ECSCA - Ten Principles of Citizen Science (ECSCA, 2015) (continued)

5. Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.
6. Citizen science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for. However unlike traditional research approaches, citizen science provides opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation of science.
7. Citizen science project data and meta-data are made publicly available and where possible, results are published in an open access format. Data sharing may occur during or after the project unless there are security or privacy concerns that prevent this.
8. Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.
9. Citizen science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact.
10. The leaders of citizen science projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities.

Using the ECSCA Ten Principles and a published review of the principles (**Robinson, et al 2018**) as a framework of analysis a review of Cos4Cloud CO experiences was conducted based on insight gathered from survey feedback. Core terms and themes were identified and used to categorise survey questions and responses using the framework that was developed. This analysis of Cos4Cloud CO Survey contributions was collated and used to shape the following *Guidelines on best practice for citizen observatories* (**Cos4Cloud / Ansine et al, 2023**).

Guidelines on best practice for citizen observatories*: a Cos4Cloud CO approach framed by the ECSCA 10 Principles of citizen science

* Key terms quoted below are from (**ECSCA, 2015**)¹ and / or (**Robinson et al, 2018**)².

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 1: COs “use digital technologies”² to “actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour[s] that generate new knowledge or understanding”¹.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: COs use digital technologies to actively involve citizens. A clearly outlined purpose / objective, framed by the environmental or scientific topic, defines the type of observations that are contributed, and the type of data collected. A defined geographic focus and set languages available contributes to how the CO can communicate and to engages with participants. Evidence of involvement can be tracked over time through user participation and this activity

demonstrates examples that “actively involve citizens”¹ and the role they play “in scientific endeavour[s] that generate new knowledge or understanding”¹.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 2: COs contribute to research that can achieve a “science outcome”¹ supporting “learning and research”² while facilitating participation, engagement and outreach.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: Users contribute observations to COs through established protocols based on the scientific discipline / field. This provides data which is made available as a source for research i.e. scientific publications etc., that can achieve a science outcome. This also supports education and learning while facilitating participation, engagement and outreach.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 3: COs involve a range of groups who “benefit from taking part”¹ in different ways i.e. “scientific outcomes, social interaction, skills development, learning etc”².

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: COs involve professional scientists, experts citizen scientists and a range of other different groups and all can “benefit from taking part”¹ in different ways i.e. research outputs, contributing to scientific evidence, learning opportunities, skills development, personal enjoyment, etc. A range of educational, engagement and outreach tools and resources are also developed and disseminated which support participation.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 4: COs provide a platform where users can “participate in multiple stages”¹ of research.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: Participation in citizen science initiatives is defined by different typologies that can involve multiple stages. COs also facilitate engagement in different ways including crowdsourcing, validating or confirming identification of observations; as well as through social interaction which also facilitate a process of feedback. This supports collaboration i.e. through collaborative and personalised approaches and co-creation through the use of integrated tools or creating DIY devices . Lessons learned demonstrate impact in terms of participation in different levels and multiple stages of the scientific process.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 5: COs involve users and provide “feedback”¹ as part of the process of engagement and participation.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: CO user involvement is supported and encouraged through both giving and receiving feedback to and from users, as a two-way process of engagement. Options for users to provide this is an important part of the participatory process also. For example many COs, particularly those focused on biodiversity, feedback as validation agreement etc is part of the crowdsourcing of identifications within the community as part of the ID process. However, more structured public feedback is integrated as part of engagement and outreach i.e. news, social media etc.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 6: COs are an important part of the citizen science scene. They make contributions as “research”¹ infrastructures therefore similar control of “limitations and biases”¹ apply.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: COs are an important part of the development and growth of citizen science. They make contributions as research infrastructures therefore similar control of “limitations and biases”¹ apply. Data management is a core consideration to ensure that relevant guidance and measures are implemented to reduce possibilities for errors and bias as well as increase the validity and accuracy of citizen science data.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 7: COs promote “open data”² and “metadata”¹ practices while ensuring that data is accessible and “publicly available”¹.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: COs endeavour to promote open data and work together on metadata practices while ensuring that data is accessible and publicly available. CO data is made available using web-based applications and technology. How COs manage data as well as the licences used for sharing are also key.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 8: COs have built in “recognition”² systems which acknowledge¹ user contributions and communicates results from the user community

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: Theme 8: COs have built in “recognition”² systems i.e. user badges, which acknowledge and recognise their contributions. User observations and other metrics are recorded, monitored and tracked using different tools. Information and results are communicated acknowledging the user community in publications etc.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 9: CO’s conduct “evaluation”² in different ways: studies on impact, use of data as a “scientific output”¹, etc; experiences and stories are also sometimes documented towards understanding “wider societal or policy impact”¹

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: Although not always possible to do, CO’s conduct “evaluation” documenting outcomes in different ways: studies on impact, use of data, etc. Engagement and participation experiences and user stories are also sometimes documented as user cases. Through their actions COs demonstrate interest in collecting and sharing stories as a contribution to evaluating impact as well as towards understanding and communicating “wider societal or policy impact”¹.

Cos4Cloud CO Guideline 10: COs consider “legal and ethical issues”¹ in their design, development and management. “Ethical matters”² are an important consideration in the process of collating and sharing user contributions.

Cos4Cloud COs best practice characteristics: COs consider legal and ethical issues as part of the technical development, management and sustainability. Intellectual property, data sharing and attribution as well as ethical matters are all important considerations. This is particularly relevant in the process of engaging participation while collating and sharing user contributions as observations supporting environmental monitoring.

COS4CLOUD CO GUIDELINES AND CHARACTERISTICS: EXAMPLES OF CURRENT BEST PRACTICE

The nine COs involved in Cos4Cloud present a range of characteristics, experiences and best practice that further demonstrate the guidelines. Examples which can be of relevance to other COs, include the following:

01

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 1: A common feature of COs is the use of **digital technologies** and the COs in Cos4Cloud each have clearly outlined and expressed objectives and a defined purpose engaging different target groups. Documenting observations within specified fields / disciplines / topics they are collecting geographically located data that over time can inform understanding of these topics while generating new knowledge. For example, with a focus on biodiversity monitoring, **Artportalen** is a reporting system for species observations and data collection focused on Sweden’s natural history. **iSpotnature** was developed to encourage and support people to record and learn about wildlife as well as how to identify and **Natusfera** shares biodiversity learning with its community while **Pl@ntNet** monitors plant biodiversity and facilitates access to plant knowledge. While focusing on environmental monitoring **CanAirIO** creates and develops manuals for building DIY devices for citizen science; **FreshWater Watch** monitors water quality; **iSPEX** measures aerosols with a spectropolarimeter add on; **Kduino** provides a low-cost open-source monitoring system to measure water transparency; and **OdourCollect** builds collaborative maps to tackle odour pollution issues.

02

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 2: The Cos4Cloud COs collect observations within specified protocols, and this presents data that contribute to research i.e. **real science outcomes**. For most, this has been presented at conferences etc and cited in scientific publications in different ways. For example, with **Artportalen** this has been cited as data originating from the CO platform itself, its affiliate Swedish LifeWatch or as a data download available on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). With **iSpot**, members of the team have been either co-authors and or lead authors on some papers using iSpot data; in others iSpot is cited as a source; while in others iSpot is consulted and the use of the platform itself and data acknowledged.

PI@ntNet has some similarities to iSpot: some papers have been co-authored with the team; some articles cite these publications by the team (in particular the ones about LifeCLEF challenges that regularly use PI@ntNet data). While others cite PI@ntNet in the acknowledgements or in the main text. For **OdourCollect**, many members of the affiliated D-Noses project have been cited and acknowledged in publications, both as authors and/or collaborators and **iSPEX** data has been cited in papers written by Leiden University, a lead partner.

03

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 3: The Cos4Cloud COs engage with a range of stakeholder groups who have a variety of reasons or motivations for use (i.e. contributing to data, use for educational activities, creating research, among others) and based on this benefit from taking part in different ways. The COs were able to describe the main groups involved, from a list of possibilities, including: the educational sector (i.e. schools, teachers), academic researchers, NGOs, Government, industries, amateurs, students, researchers, farmers, activists, urban citizens, others. The sustainability of COs is dependent on implementing measures to help facilitate continued engagement; this includes engagement and outreach and resources (i.e. set of guidelines, tutorials, promo / info videos, leaflets, training courses/ webinar etc) targeting these different groups.

What are the main groups that use the Cos4Cloud COs? (Ansine, 2023)

04

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 4: The COs in Cos4Cloud enable users to get involved and participate in different ways. For example in **Artportalen** this includes user contributions that inform environmental planning, decision making, research, impact assessments, Flora and Fauna Guardians, annual and status reports. **iSpot** is used in bioblitzes, biodiversity monitoring, published atlases of groups of organisms such as mammals, contributes to national reports i.e. State of Nature; analysis and reporting of different species groups etc. On **Natusfera** users participate in bioblitzes, monitoring phenology, monitoring fauna, creating their own projects (for specific purposes). With **Pl@ntNet** this involves recreational and professional usage of the Pl@ntNet App - as well as educational programs workshops/training (i.e. the Telabotanica MOOC) and various bioblitzes. **CanAirIO** supports users with air quality monitoring while FreshWater Watch facilitates monitoring, stewardship, education, and informing policy. **iSPEX** devices help users measure the polarisation of light to study air quality, and monitors water quality to detect the presence of certain particles or substances in the water, (i.e. algae, bacteria, or pollution). While **OdourCollect** is used to register observations regarding odours affecting where people live, allowing them to participate in research that impacts on their lives.

05

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 5: COs allow open exploration of the observations and data available on the platform using the tools and features available. Registration is an important part of this process as it gives participants access to post observations, add comments, participate in forum discussions etc. In terms of feedback from the CO this can be publicly available provided in bespoke news sections of the CO platform as well as regular updates on activities as via social media. Feedback is provided in different ways, for example, in **Artportalen** this is reflected in how data is used i.e. environmental planning, decision making and published scientific articles. Some COs also provide dynamic participatory feedback processes. For example on **iSpot** the user community and CO team can communicate via iForum Live synchronous chat discussions. In **Natusfera** users have a dedicated blog service, where they can write their opinions that are available to the rest of the community.

06

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 6: Data management is a core consideration to ensure that relevant guidance and measures are implemented to reduce possibilities for errors and bias. Validity and accuracy of data and how this can be assured were a key consideration for the COs in Cos4Cloud in terms of considering the main lessons learned in terms of ensuring reliability and what works or doesn't towards ensuring trustworthy data and information. From the perspective of **Pl@ntNet** it is necessary to have a clean data model and an efficient database structure, the data acquisition step is crucial to improving data quality. It was noted that with a smaller percentage of observations revised for accuracy due to the skill sets in botany required, it is necessary to have an estimation of the skill level of each contributor to help assess data quality. However on Pl@ntNet "the vast majority of contributors are outperformed by AI algorithms in terms of plant identification performance - the collected data is always of heterogeneous quality and data post-filtering is always necessary" (Pl@ntNet comments in CO Survey 1, June 2020 in Ansine, 2023).

07

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 7: COs promote open data and work together on metadata practices and principles while ensuring that data is accessible and publicly available. For COs, ensuring data is made available using web-based applications and technology is a core characteristic and part of how they are designed and implemented. Many implement data management plans governed by GDPR and have outlined process that governs the storage of data governed by CO management. How the Cos4Cloud COs manage and share data is mostly outlined in the CO user terms and conditions and use can vary based on the type of data collected (i.e. whether images are included) and use for research purposes. For example, **Artportalen** facilitates open data, but image copyright lies with the reporter. The creation of **iSpot** content (except images) which includes the use and collection of iSpot data are governed by the iSpot Terms of Use and Privacy Policy. The specific licence that iSpot uses is CC BY-NC 4.0. While on **Natusfera** users can choose among different options, from private to CC and **OdourCollect** facilitates open data for citizens observations.

08

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 8: COs have built in recognition systems which are mechanisms to manage and acknowledge contributors. For example on **Artportalen** all data is open with the exception of observations concerning sensitive species that are hidden within the system and only visible to the reporter and those with appropriate access privileges; no data is anonymous. **iSpot** has an integrated 'reputation management' system which provides user-feedback on likely identifications, as users enhance their own identification skills. Users are badged depending on the level of reputation they have gained and which recording schemes they represent. This information is available on their public profile and in each interaction with an observation. The platform is supported by a curator who helps to provide oversight of an active online community. Participants can acknowledge support from others through the comments and forums.

09

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 9: Engagement and participation experiences and stories are also sometimes documented as user cases to towards understanding and communicating "wider societal or policy impact". Studies are sometimes conducted to evaluate impact this includes examples that demonstrate CO contributions to policy making or similar activity and lesson learned in terms of engagement and participation See example of **Pl@ntNet** Impact Study below:

*Pl@ntNet Impact study: evaluation

The study was conducted to measure the impact of the initiative. We surveyed a large panel (several hundred) of Pl@ntNet users among the ones who created a user profile. We completed this survey with a usage analysis (based on google analytics tools) and several focus groups and interviews with representatives from different domains: (i) scientific field (ecology, computer science) and citizen science, (ii) agriculture, (iii) biodiversity management, (iv) education.

This impact study revealed:

Pl@ntNet is used monthly in all countries of the world, although it is most widely used in Europe and North America. A majority of users use Pl@ntNet for their leisure time, which

illustrates the important benefit of this research project for the non-academic community. This may explain the peaks in usage observed since 2013, on weekends and holidays. A majority of users used Pl@ntNet in their outdoor activities, such as in their garden, or during their hikes. This recreational activity is motivated by a variety of factors ranging from a stronger immersion in nature to gastronomy or phyto-therapy. 12% of Pl@ntNet users use it for their professional activities (which represents a volume of more than 6,000,000 sessions mobilised for professional activities considering the total number of sessions of more than 55M). The most frequently represented professional activity is landscape management (for landscape designers, managers, architects, as well as foresters).

A second important category concerns the group of people investing in the production and/or transfer of knowledge such as teachers (botany, biology, computer science), students (e.g. horticultural production), trainers (landscaping, aromatherapy, herbalism, medicine, etc.), facilitators (botanists, nature guides) and scientists (mainly biologists and computer scientists).

10

Cos4Cloud CO best practice: Guideline 10: Aligned with some of the themes from the guidelines above, the COs in Cos4Cloud consider legal and ethical issues as part of their technical development, management and sustainability. In terms of the protocols / standards that COs adhere to or implement; considerations around how privacy is managed and data shared as well as user terms and conditions around copyright, intellectual property, data sharing are key. Meeting the technological challenges of COs is a key aim of Cos4Cloud associated with ensuring [interoperability](#) which is impacted by the technical differences i.e. programming language as well as the protocols and standards each CO adheres to.

COS4CLOUD CO GUIDELINES AND CHARACTERISTICS: CONCLUSION AND IDEAS FOR FUTURE APPLICATION

Citizen science supports and provides opportunities for anyone to get involved with scientific research and is recognised as a means towards public participation and engagement with science. Defined by different frameworks and typologies it has been suggested that participation in COs occurs through different stages or levels of participation ([Haklay, 2013](#)) crowdsourcing (i.e. citizens inputting observations as sensors); distributed intelligence - citizens providing more input (i.e. validation which can be supported by training offered through web-based resources); participatory citizen science which engages participants in additional steps collecting, analysing as well as think of research questions; and finally collaborative or 'extreme' citizen science which provides integration at all levels.

The COs in Cos4Cloud enable users to get involved in different ways encouraging “the participation of citizens in data collection, data interpretation and information delivery” using an ICT infrastructure (Liu et al, 2017). In addition to this COs provide different types of opportunities or roles for participation as makers (i.e. developing Do-it-Yourself tools), observers (i.e. use the technology available to provide observations) or analysers (i.e. interpreting or validating information) (Monimo et al, 2017).

The framework outlined above, presented in the context of the ECSA Ten Principles, therefore is a useful model for consideration when presented in alignment and as an extension to the characteristics of COs that have been identified in previous work. Developed and informed by insight from two surveys conducted to better understand the role and context of the nine COs associated with the project, the also act as a mechanism that explores these characteristics from the experiences of the COs themselves. The surveys were developed as a structured way to gather common attributes and characteristics i.e. the aim, geographic scope, project duration, target groups, what they monitor, and type of data collected as well as how data is collected, interpreted, visualised disseminated and the technologies used to do so.

Both surveys also presented information on the engagement of participants, public participation in scientific research, while facilitating knowledge sharing, learning and building skills, etc. This is viewed as an important part of the growth of COs, playing a significant role in biodiversity recording and environmental monitoring (Gold, 2018; WeObserve, 2021). This has also helped to inform understanding of the impact of Cos4Cloud as a methodology contributing to **D6.2 Guidelines on Best Practice for COs as part of the Outreach Methodology Report** (Ansine, 2023) as well as the development of best practice guidelines in [The Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#).

REFERENCES, ADDITIONAL INFORMATION, LINKS AND FURTHER SUPPORT:

Cos4Cloud Consortium (2023). Ansine, J., Fabo Cartas, C., Soucha, K., Guidelines on Best Practice for COs as part of the Outreach Methodology Report (D6.2). Co-designed Citizen Observatories Services for the EOS-Cloud (Cos4Cloud).

ECSA (European Citizen Science Association). (2015). Ten Principles of Citizen Science. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>. https://zenodo.org/record/5127534#.Y_eAYa2ZNPZ

Gold, M. (2018). D2. 1 EU citizen observatories landscape report—frameworks for mapping existing CO initiatives and their relevant communities and interactions. Zenodo. DOI, 10.

Haklay, M., 2013, Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information – overview and typology of participation in Sui, D.Z., Elwood, S. and M.F. Goodchild (eds.), 2013. *Crowdsourcing Geographic Knowledge: Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) in Theory and Practice*. Berlin: Springer. pp 105-122 DOI: 10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7

Liu, H. Y., Kobernus, M., Broday, D., & Bartonova, A. (2014). A conceptual approach to a citizens' observatory—supporting community-based environmental governance. *Environmental Health*, 13, 1-13.

Mominó, J. M., Piera, J., & Jurado, E. (2017). Citizen observatories as advanced learning Environments. *Analyzing the Role of Citizen Science in Modern Research*, 192-212.

Piera, J., & Cos4Cloud Consortium. (2020). Integrating Citizen Science in the European Open Science Cloud 'Cos4Cloud': a minimum viable ecosystem (MVE) for tackling common challenges of citizen observatories. (Accessed at: <https://digital.csic.es/handle/10261/240848>).

Robinson, L.D., Cawthray, J.L., West, S.E., Bonn, A. and Ansine, J., 2018. Ten principles of citizen science. In *Citizen science: Innovation in open science, society and policy* (pp. 27-40). UCL Press

Sturm U, Schade S, Ceccaroni L, Gold M, Kyba C, Claramunt B, Haklay M, Kasperowski D, Albert A, Piera, J., Brier J, Kullenberg C, Luna S (2017) Defining principles for mobile apps and platforms development in citizen science. *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 3: e21283. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.3.e21283>

WeObserve consortium (2021). Roadmap for the uptake of the Citizen Observatories' knowledge base. Report submitted to the European Commission. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4646774

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 863463.